
Unlocking Potentials of Fishermen for Ensuring Livelihood Sustainability through a Multi-Pronged Approach to Empowering Artisanal Fisheries in Shiroro Dam Communities, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The paper unlocks the Potential of fishermen to ensure sustainability through a multi-pronged approach to empowering artisanal fishermen in Shiroro Dam communities, Nigeria. A questionnaire schedule was employed to gather information from 460 participants. Techniques for proportionate and multi-stage sampling were employed to choose the respondents. Data analysis was done using both inferential statistics, such as linear regression, and descriptive statistical methods, such as frequency distribution count, percentages, and mean. The study's findings demonstrated that the majority of respondents (51.3%) were between the ages of 29 and 41, suggesting that the respondents were youthful, middle-aged fishermen who are still considered to be of fishing age. (87.0%) of the respondents reported being married, and their typical household consisted of 13 people. Four of the eight factors in the model (household size, X^1 , access to extension, X^2 , fishing experience, X^3 , and association membership, X^4) were found to be significant at both the 1% and 5% levels of significance, according to logit regression estimates of the determinants of fish catch. As a result, the research concluded that artisanal fishing is vital to the livelihoods of the fishermen around the two dams and must be continued. Therefore, the study suggested that financial institutions provide credit facilities to fishermen who are actively engaged in fishing, and that the requirements for obtaining such credit be simplified. Fishermen should receive enhanced fishing and processing inputs from the government at a discounted cost. Fishermen should be educated about new fishing methods by Fisher Extension Agents.

Key Words: Fishermen, Livelihood Sustainability, Multi-Pronged Approach, Artisanal Fisheries, Shiroro Dam

INTRODUCTION

The federal government of Nigeria has executed a number of initiatives aimed at augmenting the local fish supply with great success. The second and third phases of the Fadama program are among the projects. While there have been some improvements noted in terms of fish output, the artisanal fishery, which provides the majority of the nation's protein from fish despite Nigeria's population growth, and the use of traditional fishing methods have resulted in a growing gap between the supply and demand for fish. Nigeria's fisheries industry, particularly its marine sector, supports the country's economic growth and the socioeconomic development of its citizens by increasing the GDP (Stanley, 2019). According to Tafida *et al.*, (2011), Nigeria has an abundance of marine fisheries resources that could contribute to a rise in the quantity and quality of fish produced. In 2018, the global fish and fisheries products export market was valued at US\$85.9 billion, a real increase of 98% between 1990 and 2019. The fishing business is largely dominated by developing nations. According to estimates from the Food and Agriculture Organization (Akeredolu, 2019), 79% of fisheries production occurred in developing nations in 2018, which also accounted for 49% of global fish and fish product exports in terms of value and 59% in terms of quantity.

METHODOLOGY

Details of the Shiroro Data

The Shiroro Dam is where the study was conducted. With a 3.2% growth rate, the population of Shiroro is expected to reach 322,918 by 2020 (NPC, 2006). Most of Nigeria's staple crops, including maize, yam, rice, millet, and sorghum, can be grown there thanks to the state's climate, edaphic features, and hydrology, which also provide ample opportunities for harvesting freshwater fish like *Tilapia* spp., *Bagrus* spp., *Clarias* spp., *Gymnarchus niloticus*, *Heterotis* spp., *Labeo* spp., *Mormyris* spp., and *Latesniloticus*. Located in the Shiroro Gorge of Shiroro Local Government, Niger State, the Shiroro hydropower reservoir is a storage-based hydroelectric project about between latitudes 9° 57' 25N and longitudes 6° 49' 55E. It is situated on the Dinya River about 90 kilometers southwest of Kaduna.

Size of Sample and Procedure for Sampling

296 fishing settlements along the Shiroro dam were found by the survey. There are 3,632 fishermen living in the fishing settlements of Shiroro (NSMARD, 2022). The sampling frame, represented by this figure (3,632), is what was used to determine the study's sample size. Proportionate and multi-stage sampling methods were used in the investigation. First of all, the dam was purposefully chosen for the North Central region, which is home to a large artisanal fishing industry. Shiroro is the dam. Second, a random drawing of 20 villages was made along the Shiroro dam. Thirdly, 220 fishermen were utilized as the sample size for the study along the dam after 10% of the fishing population from each of the chosen villages was chosen using the proportionate sampling technique.

Technique for Gathering Data

For the study, both primary and secondary data were employed. Using standardized questionnaires created in accordance with the goals of the study, primary data was collected. The respondents who were chosen for the study were given copies of it.

Methods of Data Analysis

Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used to examine the data that were gathered. Objective 1 was analyzed using descriptive statistics, including frequency distribution count,

percentages, mean, and ranking. Similarly, objectives 2 were analyzed using linear regression.

Analysis of Logit Regression

Model specifications

To examine goal 2, Logit Regression Analysis (LRA) was used. The relationship between a vector of independent variables (x_i) and a censored continuous dependent variable (y_i) is described by the linear model, an inferential statistical regression model.

X_i through X^{10} are the independent variables, and Y_i is the dependent variable.

The mathematical expression for the generic Logit regression model is $Y = \alpha + \beta_0 + \beta_1 X^1 + \beta_2 X^2 + \beta_3 X^3 + \beta_4 X^4 + \dots + \beta_{10} X^{10} + U$ (1), in which Y is the fish catch (kg)

X^1 = Technology kind (1 being local, 2 being improved, and 3 being merged).

X^2 = Boat type (motorized = 1, non-motorized = 0)

X^3 = Formal Education Level (Years of Schooling),

X^4 = Years of fishing experience,

X^5 = Age of the fisher,

X^6 = Number of fishermen' households,

X^7 = Access to Credit (zero if access is not granted),

X^8 = Association membership (1 for membership, 0 for non-membership),

X^9 = Exploration services access (1 for access, 0 for otherwise),

X^{10} = Fishing Season (1 during the dry season, 0 during other seasons),

U = Term of error.

Constant term = β_i ; calculated regression coefficients = $\beta_i - \beta_{10}$

FINDINGS

Table 1: Artisanal fishermen's socioeconomic characteristics (n = 460)

Factors	Frequency	Percentage	Average
The Fishermen's Age			
16---28	13	2.8	
29 – 41	236	51.3	
42 – 54	111	24.2	46.0
55 and above	100	21.7	
Total	460	100	
The Fishermen's Sexual Orientation			
Female	82	17.8	
Male	378	82.2	
Total	460	100	
Status of Fishermen's Marriages			
Married	400	87.0	
Single	41	8.9	

Divorced	6	1.3	
Widow	9	0.8	
Widower	4	2.0	
Total	460	100	
Education Level			
Elementary Instruction	65	14.1	
Education in Junior Secondary	75	16.3	
Education in Senior Secondary	150	32.6	
Higher Education	34	7.4	
Without Formal Education	136	29.6	
Total	460	100	
Size of Household			
Less than 5	69	15.0	
6 – 13	185	40.0	12.0
14 – 21	166	35.0	
22 and above	40	10.0	
Total	460	100	
Association of Fishermen’s Membership			
Member	115	25.0	
Non-Member	345	75.0	
Total	460	100	
Experience in Fishing			
Less than 5	13	2.8	
6 – 12	104	22.6	
13 – 19	119	25.9	19.0
20 and above	224	48.7	
Total	460	100	
Extension Access			
No	389	84.6	
Yes	71	15.4	
Total	460	100	
Credit Availability			
No	428	93.0	
Yes	32	7.0	
Total	460	100	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 2: Estimates of the Potentials of Fishermen for Ensuring Livelihood Sustainability through a Multi-Pronged Approach to Empowering Artisanal Fisheries (n = 460)

Potentials	Factors	The ratio	Standard error	t-value	p-value
(Constant)	X ⁰	0.886***	.070	12.660	.000
Fishing Technology	X ¹	0.003	.020	.157	.875
Boat Type	X ²	0.005	.039	.138	.890
Educational Level	X ³	0.075**	.002	.278	.781
Household Size	X ⁴	-0.006***	.002	-3.413	.001
Access to Extension	X ⁵	0.055**	.032	1.741	.082
Access to Credit	X ⁶	0.0301**	.045	.168	.867
Season of Fishing	X ⁷	0.010	.030	.319	.750
Age	X ⁸	-0.002	.002	-1.198	.232
Fishing Experience	X ⁹	0.007***	.002	3.284	.001
Membership of Association	X ¹⁰	0.058**	.025	2.317	.021
R ²		55			
F		262.200			

"Significant at the 10%, 5%, and 1% levels; significant at the*, ** and *** levels."

Source: Field survey, 2023.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Artisanal Fishermen's Socioeconomic Profiles

The fishermen's age

Because it has an impact on output, productivity, and the acceptance of innovation, age is a significant socioeconomic factor. The socioeconomic characteristics of the fishermen are displayed in Table 1. The results show that (51.3%) of the respondents are between the ages of 29 and 41, (24.2%) are between the ages of 42 and 54, (21.7%) are between the ages of 55 and above, and (2.8%), the lowest percentage of respondents in terms of age distribution structure, are between the ages of 16 and 28 with a mean of 46.5. The chart makes it clear that most of the responders are young, middle-aged fishermen who are within the active fishing age range and have the vigor and energy to significantly contribute to the development of fisheries. With a mean age of 46.5 years, the age distribution of the respondents, as displayed in the table, indicates that the majority of the fishermen were between the ages of 16 and 28. This suggests that the majority of those working in artisanal fishing were still active and capable of paddling the canoes. It follows that the respondents were able to raise fishing production and enhance the standard of living for fishing households since they were in the economically active and productive age range. This aligns with other research on fisheries, including (Stanley, 2009). Additionally, it demonstrates that the majority of fishermen in this age group are capable of engaging in rigorous artisanal fishing operations that will raise their level of living overall, income, and food security. The outcome also showed that the majority of fishermen were within the economically active age range of the population, making them a valuable labor force in artisanal fisheries given the Federal Government of Nigeria's recent efforts to boost fish output from this sector. The proportion of fishermen between the ages of 16 and 28 and 55 and older has sharply

decreased. Nonetheless, fishermen who were 55 years of age and older—the age group considered to be dependent—continued to fish. The implications of this could be attributed to the fact that many communities living close to dams rely on fishing for both their food supply and a living and that the majority of fishermen view fishing as their way of life (Shettima *et al.*, 2014).

The individuals who are actively involved in fishing tend to embrace and use contemporary fishing methods that can produce sizable fish captures. This result is consistent with that of Ifeanyi-obi and Iremesuk (2018), who found that energetic young and middle-aged fishermen are thought to be more open to embracing new technology than older fishermen who are risk adverse, cautious, and hesitant to experiment with newer technologies. The results of Shehu and Kafayat (2017) and Isaac (2018), two other artisanal fisheries studies, which also revealed that individuals in the more active age groups dominate fishing activities, are similarly consistent with this study. This study confirms the conclusions of Sampson (2013), who postulated that the bulk of the artisanal fishers in the study region were still in the prime of their lives.

The fishermen's sexual orientation

Table 1's data also revealed that men made up the bulk of respondents (82.2%), with women making up the minority (17.8%). This is particularly evident in the artisanal fishing industry, where men predominate and women work mostly in fish processing and marketing. When it comes to plunging into the sea to catch fish, male responders predominate. This research is in unison with Rosina(2018) who believes that majority (58%) of the respondents in their study were male indicating that male were more in artisanal fishing activities in the study region which demonstrated that male dominate artisanal fishing business. The results are consistent with those of Onemolease and Oriki (2011), who argued that men typically make up the majority in artisanal fisheries because they are responsible for providing for their dependents' needs, including food for the household, funds for medical care, and support for further education. Women are generally recognized for being housekeepers; they look after the kids and perform other household tasks. Because of its nature, artisanal fishing (fish catch) is not a female-friendly industry. They can't participate to the fullest extent because of this, but their main activities are fish processing, marketing, packaging, and transportation. The study also showed that, due to the nature of their work, all respondents who engaged in artisanal fishing were men. Gender is a major factor in determining the kinds of activities that men and women will participate in. Even in their pursuit of power and access to wealth, women typically steer clear of vocations that are associated with men. It was also well known that most women who entered the fish dealing and marketing industry did so since it was a comfortable endeavor for them. This could be primarily linked to their upbringing and culture (Olawumi *et al.*, 2010)

Status of the fishermen's marriages

In terms of marital status, the respondents were (87.0%) married (8.9% single), (1.3%) divorced, (0.8%) widowed, and (2.0%) widower. This result shows that a higher proportion of the respondents were married, which suggests that they were burdened with providing for the basic necessities of their families, such as making sure that their homes were supplied with food. This is consistent with the findings of Adedokun *et al.*, (2016), who also discovered that the majority of artisanal fishers (73%) were married, suggesting that many of them had family obligations and, as a result, had a propensity to give up on artisanal fishing if sufficient funds were not forthcoming to support their families. Isaacs (2018) findings are consistent with this study, which found that men predominate in artisanal fishing. According

to the results, the majority of respondents (73.3%) were married, while (25.8%) were single and just 1% were separated. This suggests that the majority of the fishermen were married, indicating a strong commitment to the institution of marriage. The majority of fishing households surveyed saw artisanal fishing as a family industry, with most family members having fished at some point. The fishermen's marital status had a significant impact on their productivity since family members could help with fishing. In order to supplement their income and maintain their standard of living, the sampled respondents also participated in other economic endeavors.

Olaoye (2010) found that the majority of the fishermen in their study were married, suggesting that artisanal fishing is primarily a married activity. This demonstrates the strong regard for the institution of marriage and points out the respondents' financial obligations to take care of their dependents. The study's additional finding indicates that married respondents showed a greater interest in fishing than single respondents. This could be because most respondents depend on fishing to meet their basic needs since they are more likely to be married and to be more devoted to their homes because they depend on water for their livelihood. The single person may not have a passion for fishing; instead, they may have worked at other jobs in the adjacent cities or urban areas to support themselves. Nigeria boasts 14 million hectares of inland waters, rivers, and lakes, but artisanal fisheries are still underdeveloped in the majority of these areas, many of which are bordered by impoverished people in need of aid (Olaoye *et al.*, 2012).

The fishermen's educational attainment

According to Table 1's results, (14.1%) of respondents had only completed their primary education, (16.3%) had completed their junior secondary education, (32.6%) had completed their senior secondary education, (7.4%) had completed their tertiary education, and the other respondents had not completed any education at all with (29.6%) only having adult or Qur'anic education instead of any formal schooling. Their livelihood can be affected by this to some degree. The respondents' demand for and access to bank credit as well as their interactions with extension agents may be impacted by their low level of education. Adedokun *et al.* (2016) and Bolarinwa (2014), in two different studies, corroborate this finding by demonstrating that the majority of artisanal fisheries operators only completed secondary education. According to Isaac (2018), educated fishermen should be more open to accepting and implementing innovations and making better use of resources. The study's respondents' low educational attainment is in line with Akankali and Jamabo's (2011) findings, which indicate that. This work complies with the Cross River basin report by Oladimeji and Abubakar (2020). On the other hand, Adedokun *et al.* (2016) stated that education is a crucial social and economic instrument for development. It is an ongoing process of development and is crucial to the adoption of new technologies. The results showed that the majority of the artisanal fishermen in the research area only completed secondary school, which has no positive effect on their productivity levels or acceptance of new technologies. Despite having completed secondary school, the majority of the fishermen in the study area did not have very high literacy rates. Fishermen with formal education possess fundamental knowledge of fishing operations, making it simpler for them to assimilate advances from research institutes and extension agents for optimal output. The country's demand for a significant expansion of its domestic artisanal fisheries from interior waterways can only be fulfilled with the help of education. Sustainable development benefits from education (Oladimeji *et al.*, 2013). The respondents' low level of formal education included tertiary degree, which is deemed necessary for fishermen to boost productivity.

Fishermen's lack of formal education has an impact on their awareness of and acceptance of contemporary fishing methods.

According to Okeowo *et al.*'s (2015) research, education plays a crucial role in influencing fishermen's decisions to engage in artisanal fishing activities. This is because education affects fishermen's awareness, perception, acceptance, rejection, and/or adoption of innovations that have the potential to increase or decrease fish output. Education helps fishermen easily grasp new fishing practices and increases their receptivity to guidance from extension organizations or technical recommendations that need a certain level of literacy and numeracy. The results corroborate those of Adaka *et al.*, (2014), who suggested that education level may have a beneficial effect on how people behave. They went on to say that formal education has a positive and significant impact on fishermen's efficiency when fishing, and that a sizable portion of fishermen lack formal education, which makes it unlikely that they will accept and use newly introduced fishing techniques. In fact, only 29.6% of respondents reported having no formal education. They only received adult education to acquire skills and Qur'anic education for moral upbringing.

The fishermen's household size

The results in this table showed that, among respondents, (40.0%), or the majority, have 6–13 people living in their households; (35.0%) have 14–21 people living in their households; (10.0%) have 22 people or more living in their households; and (15.0%) have fewer than 5 people living in their households. The availability of timely, inexpensive, and free labor for fishing homes is correlated with bigger family sizes; in this scenario, larger families are probably more efficient and productive. Even while this contributed to a rise in fish production, the household also consumed a sizable quantity of fish, which decreased the revenue of the household as a whole. This is consistent with Inoni and Oyeide (2002) and Ogbe and Odiba. (2016). Greater household sizes result in more crew members being available for inland fishing, which increases fish harvest compared to smaller homes. This is a major factor in the efficient labor supply for artisanal fisheries activities. The comparatively large family sizes of the tested fishermen may be a considerable advantage in terms of the labor required for artisanal fishing in the research area. The results corroborate the big family size predominance among rural impoverished fishermen around both dams. This study supports the findings of Obande *et al.*, (2005), who hypothesized a relationship between household size and the availability of seasonal labor, lower fishing costs, and ultimately higher profits. The conclusion of the study is that fishing performance improves with smaller household sizes because more time is spent fishing and less time on family matters. This result is consistent with the study by Adedokun *et al.* (2016), which claimed that the chance of labor efficiency for fishermen increased with household size. Family members were the most frequent source of labor in the research area. The fishermen in this study may have maintained a modest family size because they are aware of family planning and because there is still a push to maintain moderate family sizes. This study supports the findings of Akeredolu (2019), who found a relationship between family size and timely labor availability; larger families are therefore probably more productive. However, because there is a shortage of fishing labor, a large household with a higher proportion of female dependents may find it more difficult to fish effectively. This is due to the fact that men predominate in Nigerian artisanal fishing.

Association of Fishermen's Membership

The findings also showed that, of the fishermen, (75.0%) do not belong to any kind of fishing association, whilst only (25.0%) do belong to one type of group. The results show that most

fishermen do not belong to any kind of cooperative association, despite the fact that these organizations are crucial to fishermen because they can provide funding, information and training for better fishing methods, inspiration, and fishing gear. This suggests that fishermen who engage with other members of their organization may learn things that enable them to increase their output (Mustapha and Ahmadu, 2017). This may be the cause of the fishermen's poor fishing productivity between the two dams, in addition to the fact that the majority of them just completed secondary school. In order to increase fish catch, fishermen have been encouraged to join cooperatives or fishing organizations in their varied locales in recent years by the efforts of fishermen's extension operations in the study regions. While some of the fishermen had previously belonged to these organizations, many of them were expelled, maybe as a result of small disputes brought on by the unsatisfactory leadership of group leaders who did not support all of the members. Even though they belonged to cooperatives or fishing clubs, they fished as individuals. As a result, they thought that when it came to plunging into the sea to capture fish, belonging to the fishing group might not really matter. A cooperative society is a social structure that facilitates fishermen's pooling of resources to gain access to inputs and understanding of their fishing problems FAO (2019). The findings of Adaka *et al.*, (2014), who suggest that cooperative membership promotes the adoption of improved fishing technologies and poverty reduction, are not supported by this study. His research also reveals that, in the study locations, the vast majority of sampled respondents (100%) do not belong to any registered or unregistered group, which may be due to a lack of awareness and interest. Therefore, membership in an association group may put fishermen under social pressure to use new technology. The results of Marbel *et al.* (2018), who noted that groups guarantee that members gain benefits from the groups in which they cannot derive individually if working alone, are likewise consistent with this survey. Since it is simpler to transmit information to a group than to an individual fisher, the fact that more than 25% of the farmers did not have group status and instead functioned as ordinary members may have an impact on their ability to get credit facilities and adopt new technology. Between the two study areas, there were notable disparities in the fishermen' group's position.

The fishermen's experience in fishing

Experience is crucial for every business, but it's extremely crucial for artisanal fishing. Because expertise gives fishermen access to knowledge about fishing spots and currents in the water, it is seen as having a significant part in the sport of fishing. The majority of respondents (48.7%) had more than 20 years of experience fishing, as indicated by Table 1's data on the number of years of experience. The largest percentage of respondents (2.8%) have fewer than 5 years of experience, with a mean of 19.09; the next highest percentage (25.9%) have between 13 and 19 years; and the lowest percentage (22.6%) have between 6 and 12 years. The respondents' age distribution suggests that they are comparatively new to the industry. In order to capitalize on more profitable fish species found in deeper waterways, artisanal fishermen must possess sufficient experience. According to Isaac (2018), fishermen with a lot of experience should be able to set reasonable targets for their businesses' development. The table also revealed that (48.7%) of the respondents had been involved in artisanal fishing for more than 20 years. This suggests that they had a great deal of experience, as one gains more expertise in a certain activity with age. The findings of Adaka *et al.*, (2014) corroborate this finding.

Experience plays a common role in fishing since it gives heads of household knowledge about fishing locations, fish migration patterns, and water currents. Fishermen with experience will be able to forecast when fish prices will be high in the market and will also be

able to build superior fishing abilities. However, the action of catching fish will be more difficult for individuals who have less fishing experience. Previous research on the importance of increasing small-scale fishing families' productivity by Bolarinwa (2014) revealed that fishing expertise could also improve one's capacity to maneuver or manipulate gears properly for a better catch. This result is in line with that of Akeredolu (2019), who found that 45.0% of respondents had between one and five years of experience fishing, and 50.0% had between six and ten years. Therefore, it stands to reason that the individuals with the most years of experience would be more skilled and knowledgeable about fish farming operations. The respondents with more years of expertise were also able to predict the state of the market when they would be able to charge more for their goods. In the early stages of a fishing business, those with less experience—especially those with fewer than five years—faced numerous risks. The average experience of the responders in artisanal fishing was 16.6 years. This suggests that they had a great deal of experience, as one gains more expertise in a certain activity with age. Experience lowers business and management risks, according to Inoni and Oyeide (2007). Isaac (2018), Adaka *et al.*, (2014), and Adedokun *et al.*, (2016) concur that experience is essential and greatly contributes to the success of any organization.

Fishermen's access to extension services

Only (15.4%) of fishermen had contact with extension services, according to the statistics in this table, whilst (84.6%) of respondents had no interaction at all with extension agents. Through recurring capacity-building programs aimed at increasing fishing efficiency, extension agents play a crucial role in educating fishermen about new fishing practices. The bulk of the fishermen who were questioned, however, did not have access to extension agents, which had a knock-on effect on their production levels for catching fish and other artisanal fishing pursuits. Fishermen can learn the tactics to use to efficiently utilize water resources from extension teachings. Additionally, it will teach fishermen how to steer clear of potentially harmful aquatic species and turbulence that could affect their fishing operations. This study is consistent with Adaka *et al.* (2014), who found that (85.63%) of respondents had never benefited from services related to fishery extension. He claims that as there would be no extension materials on the sustainable exploitation of fishery resources, the lack of extension services would have a detrimental effect on fishing. This result is consistent with the findings of Bolarinwa (2014), who felt that the monthly interaction between the respondents and the extension agent was very inadequate, with as many as 89.7% of the respondents indicating no contact at all. The fact that the respondents had no contact with extension agents to learn new fishing tactics suggested that they were still using their old fishing methods. Akeredolu's (2019) research aligns with this study as well. He acknowledged that sixty-seven percent of the fishermen he spoke with did not have access to extension services, whereas thirty percent did. He further stated that extension services aid in the dissemination of innovations and the acquisition of technical skills by fishermen, both of which increase their productivity.

Credit availability for fishermen

When purchasing and maintaining fishing equipment, credit is crucial. According to the data in this table, only (7.0%) of respondents—the majority of respondents—had access to credit, whilst (93.0%) of respondents—the respondents—did not have any credit facility. In order to grow the fishing business and buy more fishing equipment, crafts, motorized boats, and maintenance supplies, credit facilities are essential. Additionally, it can be utilized to hire additional fishing crew members, especially from smaller households. This survey is in tandem with Adaka *et al.*, (2014) whose research revealed that 40% of the respondents received credit but from informal sources like friends, relatives and local money lenders,

while (60%) constituting the majority did not receive any credit facility but used their personal savings to run the business of fishing. This study corroborates that of Isaac (2018) who opined that majority (100%) of the respondents does not have access to capital while (80%) used their own personal savings as investment capital in the study area. Credit is important for the acquisition and maintenance of fishing crafts and gears. Because of the diminishing amount of fish caught, artisanal fishing generates relatively little revenue. Because of the difficult economic realities and conditions in the nation at the time, fishermen turned to borrowing as a means of addressing their socioeconomic challenges. Fishers are not able to fulfill the prerequisites in order to apply for agricultural loans. They lack sufficient assets and guarantors to satisfy the collateral requirements needed to obtain the requested financing from the banks. Just (7.0%) of the respondents said they got credit from friends, family, or cooperatives in their community. The lack of credit lending institutions in the two research locations—Kainji and Shiroro—is most likely the cause of this. According to the respondents, loan is necessary to boost operating capital so they can buy fishing inputs, the cost of which has skyrocketed. The fishermen interpret this as meaning that having access to credit could have a long-term detrimental effect on their ability to make a living.

The Potentials of Fishermen for Ensuring Livelihood Sustainability through a Multi-Pronged Approach to Empowering Artisanal Fisheries in Shiroro Dam Communities

The regression findings of the potential of fishermen for ensuring livelihood sustainability through a multi-pronged approach to empowering artisanal fisheries in Shiroro Dam communities are displayed in Table 2. The corrected R and F values, as well as the derived R square value, led to the selection of linear regression analysis. With (55%) accuracy, the model predicted the factors influencing fish catch. In terms of predictive power, the results of the linear regression shown in Table 2 showed that the model was sufficient for comprehending the factors that influence fish harvest. It was discovered that four of the eight model's factors—household size, access to extension, fishing expertise, and association membership—were significant in predicting the amount of fish captured in the research area. At the (5%) level of significance, household size had a beneficial effect on the total amount of fish caught. Large households may indicate larger subsistence needs; therefore, in order to meet their families' financial obligations, fishing effort must be raised (Adaka *et al.*, 2014). Family members may contribute a sizable portion of the labor demand in artisanal fishing due to its labor-intensive nature (Inoni and Oyaide 2007). The findings of Inoni and Oyaide (2007), who demonstrated that household size is important in explaining catch level, are consistent with this outcome. At the 5% alpha level, the coefficient of extension contact was positive and significant. According to Bolarinwa (2014), extension services include everything from the efficient transmission of technology to the establishment of robust rural organizations that have the capacity to impact fish catch levels over time and to adopt and implement group choices for the management of natural resources. At the (5%) alpha level, the fishing experience coefficient was positive and significant. According to Ifeanyi-obi and Iremesuk (2018), fishermen with more experience in the water typically have a greater understanding of the locations of fish, weather patterns, currents and tides, bottom conditions, and the best ways to catch fish. The study indicated that experience had a favorable and highly statistically significant effect on catch level, supporting this claim. A fisherman's competence at a given time of day increases with experience. This suggests that increased experience boosts productivity. Adedokun *et al.*, (2016) found that a captain with one year more experience than other fishing unit captains creates a better catch, and this observation was in line with their findings. At the (5%) level of significance, the association's coefficient of membership was significant in affecting the amount of fish caught. This study supported the conclusions of Adaka *et al.*,(2014), who pointed out that fishermen's organizations are

essential in providing fishermen with fishing methods, expertise, and knowledge; as a result, they lower transaction costs and gain from group efforts. By offering services to their members, fisher cooperative associations may have an impact on the amount of fish caught. Therefore, we anticipate that fishermen who belong to cooperatives will be comparatively more productive. The study is in line with that of Isaac (2018), who discovered that the factors that determine fish catch, such as household size (X^1), association membership (X^2), operational costs (X^3), fishing experience (X^4), and credit availability (X^5), were significant at 5%. The coefficient of household size (X^6) is positive, indicating a positive correlation between the output of women and fishers and the size of their households. This study contradicts that of Okeowo et al. (2015), who discovered that the labor-to-fish output relationship is direct and that efficient labor boosts fish output. The coefficient of labor (X^1) is significant at (5%) and positive. Capital (X^3) and education level (X^2) both have positive and substantial (5%) significance. This implies that the fish output is significantly influenced by these two factors. It implies that the production of fishing will increase with investment. This finding makes sense because education level seems to play a significant role in raising fishing productivity. Education, according to Adedokun *et al.*, (2016), boosts labor's capacity and efficiency and renders it skilled and flexible enough to meet the demands of a changing economy. It facilitates the discovery of fishermen's innate entrepreneurial spirit and hidden abilities. It improves the fishermen's comprehension and assessment of novel producing methods. According to Akeredolu (2019), who conducted his own research on the "Economic analysis of artisanal fishing enterprises in Guma LGA of Benue State in Nigeria," a formal education will make it easier to maintain accurate fishing records, read instructional materials, and interact with extension agents. This will teach fishermen and women how to use their resources efficiently. Additionally, Akankali and Jamabo (2011) discovered that when calculating the level of fish catch, the coefficient of educational attainment was positive and significant at (1%) probability. In order to increase productivity, education aids fishermen in using written information sources more easily and in learning and comprehending new fishing techniques. Adeyemo went on to confirm that, at the (5%) probability level, the coefficient of membership of association was both positive and significant.

Conclusion / Suggestions

The study focused on artisanal fishing and how it affected the fishermen's means of subsistence around Nigeria's Kainji and Shiroro dams. The survey also showed that the majority of respondents do not have access to credit facilities, which would have allowed them to purchase fishing equipment and craft at costs that are now out of reach for the typical angler. The majority of fishermen may have given up fishing in favor of jobs with extremely minimal input requirements due to the inadequate quality of these fishing tools.

1. It was discovered that the educational status of fishermen was low. In order to guarantee that students in fishing communities receive an excellent education, fishermen should be made aware of the value of education and encouraged not to use school-age children for any kind of work during school hours.
2. The government ought to offer subsidies for fishing equipment in order to mitigate the impact of the high expense of fishing vessels and equipment, which is one of the main factors impeding the efficient utilization of fishing resources in the two dams.
3. Fishery extension agents ought to counsel anglers on how to effectively leverage their abundance of fishing knowledge to increase fish landings. This might be accomplished by becoming a member of a fisheries membership association, obtaining credit facilities, and calculating the costs of all resource inputs—including fishing gear—used in fishing operations in order to accurately determine the

economic value of fishing businesses. The government should offer more extension services to encourage the nation's artisanal fishing industry.

4. It was discovered that the most significant barrier affecting artisanal fisheries in the research area was the high cost of fishing equipment. One of the most important factors impeding the efficient exploitation of fishing resources in the two dams is the high cost of fishing vessels and gear, which is why the government should provide subsidies for fishing gear.

References

- Akankali, J. A and Jamabo. N.A. (2011). A Review of Some Factors Militating Against Sustainable Artisanal Fisheries Development in Niger Delta, Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Agricultural Sciences* 3(5): 369-377
- Akanni, K.A. and J.A. Akinwumi, (2007).Determinants of Variations in Fish Catch Levels in Artisanal Fishing of Lagos State, *Nigeria Research Journal of Fisheries and Hydrobiology*, 2(1): 1-12.
- Akeredolu, M.O. (2019).Constraints to Technology Transfer in Artisanal Fisheries. Ph.D. Aquaculture Planning in Africa, ADCP/REP/75/1, pp. 61 -65.
- Abolagba, O. J and Olabimitan, B.B. (2015). Socioeconomic Analysis of Artisanal Fishermen and Fish Farmers in Lagos State, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Applied Science*, 23(4):76 – 83.
- Adaka. S.; Etim, I. N.; Nlewadim, A. A.; and Olele, N. F. (2014). Assessment of Fish Landing by Artisanal Fishers in Owerri-Nta River, Abia State. Proceedings of the 29th Annual Conference of Fisheries Society of Nigeria. Makurdi.24th – 28th November 2014. Pp. 2
- Adedokun, O. A., Adereti, F.O and Opele, A.I. (2016). Factors Influencing the Adoption of Fisheries Innovations by Artisanal Fishermen in Coastal areas of Ogun State, *Nigerian Journal of Applied Science Research*, 2(11): 966-971
- Bolarinwa, J.B (2014).Public Relations and Extension Services in Nigerian Fisheries Industry. *International Journal of Agricultural Research* 9(7):327-330.
- Bolarinwa, J.B. (2011).Diet Composition and Food habits of African Catfish, *Clarias Gariepinus* in Fresh Water area of Epe Lagoon, Lagos State. *Journal of Vocational Education* 4 (1):23- 28.
- Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) (2019)
- Ifeanyi-Obi, C.C. and Iremesuk, P. (2018). Environmental Factors Influencing Artisanal Fishing in Eastern Obolo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. *Journal of Agricultural Extension* 22 (1):1-13
- Inoni O.E. and Oyeide W. J. (2007). Socio-Economic Analysis of Artisanal Fishing in the South Agro-Ecological zone of Delta State, Nigeria. *Agricultura Tropica et Subtropica*. 40(4):135.
- Isaac G.B (2018). *Bio-economic Analysis of Artisanal Marine Fisheries of Tanzania*. An M.Sc. Thesis Submitted to the Department of Economics, Nowegian College of Fishery Science, and University of Tromso, Norway in Partial Fulfilment of the Requirements for the Award of Master of Science Degree in International Fisheries Management.
- Mabel, O.I., Adams, O.I and Babajide, I. (2018). Economic Analysis of Artisanal Fisheries in Some Selected Fishing Communities of Ilesa Local Government Area of Ondo State. *International Journal of Development and sustainability* 7(2). Pp 716 – 723

- Mustapha, S. and Ahmadu, A.T. (2017). Artisanal Fisher Folks Perception of the Effects of Variability in Climatic Factors on Fish yield in Kainji Lake Basin, Nigeria. *Journal of Agribusiness and Rural Development* 4 (46):825 – 833
- National Population Commission. (2006) Census Publication. Pp.22
- Niger State Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development. (2022). *Policy Document for Repositioning the Fisheries Sub-sector of the Agricultural Sector of the State*. A Publication of the NERDC, 2022 Pp 50-64
- Obande R.A, Tiamiyu L.O, Itode S.O. (2005). *The Role of Women in Artisanal Fisheries along the Lower Benue River*. A Paper Presented in the 19th Annual Conference of Fisheries Society of Nigeria, 29TH November – 3rd December; 2005. Occasional Paper No. 26 Pp.8
- Ogbe, F.G and Odiba, J.Y. (2016). *The Role of Extension in Fisheries Development among Rural Communities*. Proceedings of the 13th Annual Conference of the Fisheries Society of Nigeria. Pp.87
- Okeowo, T.A., Bolarinwa, J.B. and Ibrahim, D. (2015). *Socioeconomic Analysis of Artisanal fishing and Dominant fish Species in Lagoon waters of EPE and Badagry areas of Lagos state*. Pp.43-46
- Oladimeji, Y. U., Abdulsalami, Z. and Damisa, M. A. (2013). Socioeconomic Characteristics and Returns to Rural Artisanal Fishery Households in Asa and Patigi Local Government areas of Kwara State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Science and Nature*. 4(3): 445-455.
- Oladimeji, Y.U and Abubakar, B.A.Y. (2020). The Impact of Shiroro Dam Project on Food Security and Poverty Status of Rural Fisher Folks in North Central Region of Nigeria. *Applied Tropical Agriculture Journal* 25(1):43 – 53
- Olaoye, O. J., Idowu, A. A., Omoyinmi, G. A. K., Akintayo, I. A., Odebiyi, O. C., and Fasina, A.O.(2012). Socio-Economic Analysis of Artisanal Fisher Folks in Ogun Water-Side Local Government Areas of Ogun State, Nigeria. *Global Journal of Science Frontier Research Agriculture & Biology*, 12 (4): 12
- Olaoye, O.J, Ashley, D, S.S, Fakoya, E.O, Ikeweinwe, N.B, Alegbeye, W.O, Ashaolu, F.O and Adelaje, O.A. (2013). Socio-Economic Analysis of Fish Farming in Oyo State, Nigeria. *Global Journal of Science Frontier Research Agriculture and Veterinary Science* (13):224
- Olaoye, O.J. (2010). *Dynamics of Adoption Process of Improved Fisheries Technologies in Lagos and Ogun States*. A PhD Thesis Submitted to the Department of Aquaculture and Fisheries Management, University of Agriculture, Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria. Pp. 339.
- Olawumi, A.T, Dipeolu, A.O and Bamiro O.M. (2010). Economic Analysis of Homestead fish Production in Ogun State, Nigeria. *Journal of Humanities and Ecology*, 31(1): 13-17.
- Onemolease, E.A, Oriakhi, H.O. (2011). Prospects and Constraints of Artisanal Fishing in selected Communities in Delta State, Nigeria. *Advances in Applied Science Research* 3(2): 55-61.
- Rosina, C. (2018). *Effort Control in the Artisanal Canoe Fishery of Ghana: Implications and Likelihood of Success*. Open access Master's Thesis Submitted to the Department of Marine Affairs, University of Rhode Island in Partial Fulfilment of the Requirements for the Award of Master of Arts in Marine Affairs. Pp 1- 23
- Sampson, Y. A. (2013). *Artisanal Fishing and Livelihoods in Kwahu-Nort District*. A Thesis submitted to the Department of Geography and Rural Development, Kwame-Nkrumah University of Science and Technology Ghana in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of Master of Philosophy Pp. 111

- Shehu, L.A. and Kafayat, A.F. (2017). Small-Scale Fisheries in the Context of Traditional Post-harvest Practice and the Quest for Food and Nutritional Security in Nigeria. *Journal of Agriculture and Food Science Security*. 6(3):3 – 18
- Shettima, B.G, Mohammed S.T., Ghide A.A. and Zindam, P.L. (2014). *Analysis of Socioeconomic Factors Affecting Artisanal Fishermen around Lake Alau, Jere local government area of Borno state, Nigeria*. Pp.66-68
- Stanley, W.T.M. (2009). *Factors Influencing Choice of Fishing Location in Nankumba Peninsula: A Case Study of Gillnet and Chilimira Fisheries*. A Thesis Submitted to the Faculty of Environmental Sciences. In Partial Fulfilment of the Requirement for the Award of the Degree of Doctor of Philosophy in Fisheries Management. Pp 24 – 27
- Stanley, W.T.M. (2019). Fishing for Sustainable Livelihoods Development. *European Journal of Agriculture and Aquaculture* 7 (4):24 – 27.
- Tacoli, C. (1998). *Rural-Urban Linkages and Sustainable Rural Livelihoods*’ Carney D. *Sustainable Rural Livelihoods*’ Department Fisheries for International Development. London. Pp. 122
- Tafida, A.A, Adebayo, A.A, Musa, Y.M, Nwabeze, G.O, Nyaku, R.E and Arowa, K. (2011). *Problems Affecting Fishers Livelihood and Fisheries Development in Kainji Lake Basin*. A Conference Paper Published by FISON .Pp.65